

Toag92 has medium grain and is free of white belly. Quality is good and similar to that of Baldo, Ribe, and Krasnodorsky-424 (Table 2). ■

Table 2. Quality traits of Toag92. Bornova, Turkey.

Variety	Amylose content (%)	Protein content (%)	KOH reaction	White belly ^a
Toag92	18.8	13.7	Low	5
Baldo	16.8	9.8	Low	0
Ribe	15.6	7.8	Low	-
Krasnodorsky 424	-	7.4	Low	5

^aScored using the SES scale where 0 = no belly. 9 = more than 20% of kernel area.

KK1536-C: a modern high-yielding rice variety for irrigated lowlands in Papua New Guinea

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Out of 122 genotypes we evaluated in 1991, KK15-36-C (IR 5657-33-2/BKNDR1031-7, Nepalese in origin) performed the best

and was selected as one of six genotypes for further evaluation.

We confirmed the high yield potential (10.5 t ha⁻¹) of KK15-36-C in local and regional yield trials conducted during 1992-95. At the OISCA Farm in Kokopo, Rabaul, KK15-36-C and Ayung yielded the most of the varieties tested. At Bubia during 1991 and 1995, the variety was either highest yielding (6-7 t ha⁻¹ during 1994, 9.5 t ha⁻¹ during 1995) or at par with the highest yielding genotypes.

The variety is semidwarf (<110 cm) with medium-tillering ability. It has long (>25 cm), fully filled panicles with more than 100 grains panicle⁻¹. The 1,000-grain weight is 30 g. Its foliage remains green up to late maturity.

The variety's grains are long and medium bold, awned and translucent. The milling recovery is very good. KK 15-36-C is extremely well suited for general cultivation in the irrigated lowland fields of Papua New Guinea. ■

Birsa Dhan 201 and Birsa Dhan 202: early-maturing varieties for Bihar, India

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Birsa Dhan 201 was developed by crossing TN1/Brown Gora 23-19, and Birsa Dhan 202 by crossing Jaya/BR34. Both varieties were released during 1985 and re-released in 1995 for use in the Chotanagpur and Santhal Parganas region of Bihar, India. Birsa Dhan 201 is an early-duration variety that matures in 105-110 d under transplanting. It is nonlodging, nonshattering, and highly responsive to chemical fertilizers, yielding 3.0-3.5 t ha⁻¹. It has compact, long panicles with bold grains and white kernels. It is moderately resistant to

Performance of Birsa Dhan 202 in the All-India coordinated trials. 1989 and 1990.

Variety	Mean of different locations			
	1989		1990	
	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Days to 50% flowering	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Days to 50% flowering
Birsa Dhan 202	6.3	101	3.5	94
Vikas	6.1	99	-	-
Ratna	6.1	95	-	-
Rasi	-	-	2.6	85
Local (control)	6.2	99	3.1	92

blast, bacterial leaf blight, stem borer, and gall midge.

Birsa Dhan 202 is intermediate in plant type and provides adequate rice straw for cattle feed, as required by farmers in the region. The variety has very good seedling vigor and produces heavy, drooping panicles. It is stiff-strawed, making it resistant to lodging. The grains are long and bold. producing white kernels. It is moderately

resistant to blast, stem borer, and bacterial leaf blight, but moderately susceptible to gall midge. The variety yields reasonably well, producing 5-6 t ha⁻¹ when 40-60 kg N ha⁻¹ is applied (see table). A lot of this region has been planted to Birsa Dhan 202. Farmers have been sharing its seed with each other, increasing the area planted to it.

Both varieties have acceptable taste. and grain and cooking quality.